

Conservation of Biodiversity: The Pivotal Role Played by the Indigenous People of North-East India

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Abstract

Biodiversity and the wellbeing of indigenous people are strongly interweaved. Biodiversity is essential for sustainable development and humankind's wellbeing as it underpins the provision of food, fibre and water; it mitigates and provides resilience to climate change; it supports human health as well as provides jobs in agriculture, fisheries, forestry and many other sectors. Globally, as well as in India, there has been an alarming decline in biodiversity. Indigenous knowledge contributes to the sustainable management of lands, conserving biodiversity yet it is marginalized from decision-making and policy arenas. Indigenous people's knowledge and their contribution are not given emphasis by the policy-makers/ decision makers while advocating policies for the conservation of environment. In this regard, it is pertinent to acknowledge the role of traditional knowledge or indigenous knowledge of local/ indigenous communities which has been the base of sustaining the fragile ecosystem without much gratefulness, appreciation and recognition given the fact that it is not rooted in formal institution. This paper provides an overview that clearly portrays the active role that the indigenous people of North east India have played towards the conservation of biodiversity and the importance of proper documentation, appreciation and understanding of the indigenous practices which should be used to develop future strategies for ensuring sustainable development, conservation of biodiversity and better wellbeing of human race in this planet Earth.

Keywords: biodiversity, indigenous people, indigenous/ traditional knowledge